

DETERMINATION OF FACTORS INFLUENCING DISTORTION OF CARBURIZED QUENCHING OF STEEL SHAFTS USING DoE WITH COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

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Abstract

In the last decades several computational methods have been implemented successfully to optimize many heat treatment processes in terms of distortion. However, due to the complexity of the underlying thermo - mechanical - metallurgical interactions, the optimization of carburized quenching process still remains an open field. Here, design of experiments (DoE) can help to perform the needed simulations in a well-structured manner. The main aim of this study is to detect the influencing factors of carburizing processes on the distortion of a steel shaft. For that purpose, a 4-factor 2-level full factorial DoE was set up and analyzed for a cylindrical steel shaft made of DIN 16MnCr5 steel. Investigated factors included carbon activity in the furnace (0.9%,1.1%), carburization temperature (900°C, 950°C), time (8 h, 24 h) and oil temperature (50°C – 70°C). The results indicated carburizing time as the most significant factor for both length and diameter changes, which is succeeded by carburization temperature, oil temperature and carbon activity. Oil temperature and the case-depth are found to have an effect only on the diameter change.

1.Introduction

Shafts are heavy-duty components that are indispensable in power transmission systems. The demands of primary industries for higher load-bearing capacities, operating speeds, and longer service life constitute a big challenge for shaft manufacturers. Dimensional precision, high strength, fatigue and wear resistance are essential for a high-performance shaft. In order to fulfill these demands, the vast majority of steel shafts are heat treated and used either in case- or through-hardened condition. Heat treatment has a decisive role in determining the final properties and performance of the shaft. Distortion (undesired dimension and shape changes) is the most common problem in the heat treatment of shafts.

The carburizing process is one of the most important heat treatment processes of shafts. The increase of computer capabilities and the development of Finite-Element-software allow the simulation of case-hardening processes leading to a better understanding of the process, which enables new opportunities for the design, optimization and planning. In particular, computer simulations attract special interest to predict the effect of process parameters and part geometry on the distortion.

While the heat treatment literature includes numerous experimental and simulation studies [1-6] concerning the prediction of distortion and residual stresses in carburized parts, comprehensive analyses on influencing parameters on the distortion behavior of carburized components are still needed. In that sense, a DoE is especially helpful to identify the significant factors in a well-structured way, since the physics of the carburized quenching process is complex.

In general, DoE studies were conceived for physical experiments. On the other hand, nowadays, most of the DoE studies can also be conducted using computer simulations in a time and cost effective way. By this way, DoE's with larger number of parameters, which are practically almost impossible in the industry, can be conducted. Then, experimental DoE's can only be limited to several factors and their interactions which are filtered in the computational DoE. Moreover, computational DoE's also enables the opportunity to investigate the effects of parameters other than practically controllable parameters. For example, the influence of any material property can be investigated without affecting the other material properties, which is usually practically impossible.

Most of the experimental DoE analysis methods normally depend on the variance of the response. On the other hand, computer simulations do not inherently provide scattered results under the same set of input parameters. Thus, in order to use those methods, one has to introduce an artificial variability in the

simulations results. The most common technique for this is to run multiple simulations considering the variability in the input parameters.

This study focuses on the investigation of the influence of gas carburization and quenching parameters on the distortion of cylindrical shafts by using computer simulations. Simulations are performed in an organized way using a full factorial DoE. The effect of variability in the DoE is neglected and the evaluation was performed accordingly. The results indicate the potential of computer simulation based DoE's as an alternative to experimental DoE's.

2. Method

2.1 Simulation Procedure

The simulated component is a simple cylindrical shaft having a diameter of 47.5 mm and a length of 224 mm. The shaft material is DIN EN 16MnCr5 which is a widely used carburizing steel. The simulated process is multiple step gas carburizing process succeeded by oil quenching (Isorapid® 277HM). The temperature and the carbon activity history of the investigated carburized quenching process is illustrated in Fig. 1. All simulations were conducted using commercial heat treatment software SYSWELD® (v10.0). The simulation of the carburizing process is divided into three steps. In the first step the diffusion process of carbon was simulated. The second step contains the thermal calculation with phase transformations. Finally, the mechanical calculation has to be done leading to the stress-strain-distribution and the distortion.

Figure 1: Process chart for gas carburization process

Using the symmetries of the geometry, only 1/4 of the cylinder was modeled as shown in Figure 2 in order to improve the efficiency and the stability of the solution, this also implies that the heat transfer conditions are also assumed to be symmetric and the material behavior is isotropic.

Figure 2: FE model used in DoE studies

The geometry is meshed according to following procedure: First, a fine layer-mesh is created on the surfaces to capture the carbon and temperature gradients. Then, the core of the shaft is meshed with larger elements for computational efficiency. Both the layers and core mesh consisted of 4-noded linear axisymmetric elements.

A convergence analysis for the mesh and time step size is conducted in order to eliminate the noise in the results due to inadequate meshing and time stepping. A convergence analysis is also beneficial to find the optimal parameters which provides the accuracy required with minimum computation costs such as time and memory required. Based on the convergence analysis, the rest of the study is conducted using a FE mesh consisting of 6847 elements. The surface layers consisted of elements with a thickness of 2 mm while the core is made 0.7 mm square elements.

A surface temperature dependent heat transfer coefficient (Figure 3) is invoked for all the free surfaces of the shaft. Material data for 16MnCr5 steel is taken from the database of Visual Heat Treatment® v10 software.

Figure 3: Surface temperature dependent heat transfer coefficient

2.2. Design of Experiments

In this study, a factorial design of experiments is used to find out significant effects on distortion. A full factorial design is used as it enables the investigation of both the factors and all possible interactions between the factors. Carburization temperature, carburization time, carbon activity and the oil temperature are considered as the main factors. The factors vary on two ranges, a low range getting the sign “-”, a high range getting the sign “+” and center point “0”. Thus, a 2-level 4-factor full-factorial design with a center point is used. Parameters and their levels are tabulated in Table 1. Corresponding DoE and its results are presented in Table 2.

After studying through the design of experiments step by step, all relative changes in the shaft dimensions were investigated, especially; relative change of length and relative change of diameter. Then the results are evaluated using a probability plot according to the procedures given in [7].

Table 1. Selected parameters and their levels

Factor		Unit	-	0	+
A	Carb. Temperature	°C	900	925	950
B	Carb. Time	h	8	16	24
C	Carbon Activity (C)	wt%	0.9	1.0	1.1
D	Oil Temp.(D)	°C	50	60	70

Table 2. Design of experiments and results

Run	A	B	C	D	ΔD [mm]	ΔL [mm]
1	+	-	-	-	-0.00458	0.10813
2	-	+	-	-	-0.00273	0.10443
3	-	-	+	-	-0.00569	0.11025
4	-	-	-	+	-0.00585	0.11532
5	+	+	-	-	0.00249	0.09872
6	-	+	+	-	-0.00001	0.10013
7	+	-	+	-	-0.00233	0.10564
8	+	+	+	+	0.00589	0.09594
9	-	+	+	+	0.00094	0.09955
10	+	-	+	+	-0.00144	0.10569
11	+	+	-	+	0.00359	0.09674
12	+	+	+	-	0.00505	0.09574
13	-	-	+	+	-0.00468	0.11192
14	+	-	-	+	-0.00269	0.10703
15	-	+	-	+	-0.00134	0.10782
16	-	-	-	-	-0.00671	0.11509
17	0	0	0	0	-0.00100	0.10531

3. Results and Discussion

The results of statistical analysis are presented as Pareto charts in Fig.4 and Fig.5, where the full line indicated 95% confidence level. From the figures, it can be seen that carburization time is found as the most

significant factor for both length and diameter changes, which is followed by carburization temperature and the carbon activity.

Figure 4: Pareto-chart for effect of Length change

Figure 5: Pareto-chart for effect of Diameter change

In particular, to diameter changes, the oil temperature and the interaction between carburization temperature (A) and time (B) are also found as a significant factor, while they have negligible effect on the length change. These results can be interpreted as follows: The interaction AB is related with the case-depth and the result is probably due to large side-surface. The effect of oil temperature is mainly on the stresses developed during quenching and in a long cylinder circumferential stresses are larger than axial stresses, which lead larger plastic strains in that direction. This might be the reason for this occurrence.

4. Conclusion & Outlook

The goal of this paper was to determine the factors influencing the distortion of gas carburized steel shafts and to demonstrate the application of a DOE with heat treatment simulations. 2-level 4-factor full factorial design was used to reveal the effect of process parameters to the dimensional changes in the shaft. In the design, carburization temperature, carburization time, carbon activity and oil temperature were

considered as the control parameters, while the length and diameter changes were considered as responses. The analysis of DoE was conducted using probability plots. The results revealed carburization time as the most significant factor for both the length and diameter changes, which is followed by carburization temperature and the carbon activity. On the other hand, oil temperature and the case-depth is found to have an effect only on the diameter changes.

As mentioned in the introduction part, conventional DoE with experiments are usually performed considering the scatter in the response. In the outlook of this study, repetition of the same study using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is considered.

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